

MATRIX CRACKING IN FIBRE-REINFORCED AND LAMINATED COMPOSITES

A. Kelly
Vice-Chancellor's Office
University of Surrey
Guildford, GU2 5XH
UK

and

L.N. McCartney
Division of Materials Applications
National Physical Laboratory
Teddington, Middlesex TW11 0LW
UK

ABSTRACT

The theories of elastic cracks and of constrained cracking in composites have recently been brought together by two different sets of workers. Although they agree in most essentials, the two approaches differ importantly in the use of fracture criteria. One approach assumes a stress intensity criterion for fracture, whereas the other uses an energy balance fracture criterion which is normally used when considering the fracture of brittle materials. The two approaches to matrix cracking will be reviewed in a broader context, and also applied to the understanding of cracking in laminates.

INTRODUCTION

The theoretical framework of matrix cracking (leaving fibres intact) in a fibre reinforced composite was first given by Aveston et al [1] (to be referred to as ACK theory). This work established the relationship between the matrix-cracking strain and the various parameters which characterise the geometry and properties of the fibres and matrix. Energy principles were used to derive this relationship by considering the energy changes resulting when the matrix of the composite suddenly cracks on a plane normal to the fibre direction. More recently Marshall et al [2] have used linear-elastic fracture mechanics methods, based on a critical stress intensity factor fracture criterion, to relate the applied stress (or strain) to the size of a pre-existing matrix crack. McCartney [3] has modified the approach of Marshall et al [2] utilising an energy balance fracture criterion which Griffith [4] showed to have fundamental

importance to the fracture of brittle materials. As the length of the pre-existing matrix-crack increases to infinity this energy balance approach leads to the non-zero matrix-cracking strain predicted by ACK theory.

REVIEW OF MATRIX CRACKING THEORY

Consider a composite consisting of an isotropic matrix, having Young's modulus E_m , reinforced by aligned fibres having Young's modulus E_f . The composite contains a through-crack of length $2a$ lying in a plane normal to the fibre direction (Fig. 1).

Fig.1: Diagram of a matrix crack in a fibre reinforced composite

Let the work of fracture per unit thickness for the matrix be g_m ($= 2\gamma_m$ for a brittle matrix where γ_m is the surface energy). The fibres are of circular cross-section having radius R , and their volume fraction in the composite is V_f ; the matrix volume fraction being denoted by $V_m = 1 - V_f$. The surface to surface separation of nearest neighbour fibres is denoted by S so that

$$S = 2R \left\{ \left[\frac{\alpha}{V_f} \right]^{1/2} - 1 \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = \pi/4 = 0.785$ for a square fibre array,
 $\alpha = \pi/(2\sqrt{3}) = 0.907$ for an hexagonal array.

The Young's modulus of the composite in a direction parallel to the fibres is given by

$$E_c = E_m V_m + E_f V_f, \quad (2)$$

which assumes that the matrix and the fibres have the same value of Poisson's ratio, to be denoted by ν . The composite is subjected to a uniaxial applied stress σ_∞ in a direction parallel to the fibres.

Low Volume Fractions

Consider how the cracking of the matrix is affected when the volume fraction of fibres is increased from zero. In the absence of fibres a pre-existing crack of length $2a$ will grow unstably across the specimen when the applied stress is such that

$$\sigma_{\infty} \geq \left\{ \frac{E_m g_m}{(1-\nu^2) \pi a} \right\}^{1/2} = \sigma_C^C \quad (3)$$

where plane strain conditions are assumed. The elastic strain in the material when this occurs is such that

$$\epsilon \geq \left\{ \frac{(1-\nu^2) g_m}{E_m \pi a} \right\}^{1/2} = \epsilon_C \quad (4)$$

The result (3) is derived using the energy balance argument proposed by Griffith [4]. The stress intensity factor for a crack of length $2a$ in a plate subjected to a uniform uniaxial applied stress σ_{∞} is given by

$$K = \sigma_{\infty} \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (5)$$

and thus (3) can be expressed in the form

$$K \geq \left\{ \frac{E_m g_m}{1 - \nu^2} \right\}^{1/2} = K_{IC}^m \quad (6)$$

which is the well known stress intensity fracture criterion for brittle materials. Equations (3) and (4) define an applied stress or strain at which cracking occurs for a pre-existing crack of length $2a$. If the material contains a distribution of cracks of varying size then the relations (3) and (4) apply only to the longest crack.

Keeping the length $2a$ of the pre-existing crack fixed consider the situation arising as fibres are added to the matrix. For a very dilute distribution of fibres V_f will be small enough for the surface to surface separation of fibres given by (1) to be significantly greater than the crack length, ie. $S \gg a$. For this situation the only effect of the fibres on the crack will be to change the stress in the matrix material. Assuming that the modulus of the fibres is greater than that of the matrix ie. $E_f > E_m$, the introduction of fibres will reduce the matrix stress from the value σ_{∞} (for $V_f = 0$) to the value $E_m \sigma_{\infty} / E_C$, since it follows from (2) that for this case $E_C > E_m$. Provided that $S \gg a$ a crack of length $2a$ can be regarded as being subjected to an applied stress $E_m \sigma_{\infty} / E_C$ and it follows from (3) that the critical value σ_C^C of the applied stress for cracking is

$$\sigma_C^C = \left\{ \frac{E_C^2 g_m}{(1-\nu^2) E_m \pi a} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

On using (5) this may also be expressed in the form

$$K_{IC} = \left\{ \frac{E_C^2 g_m}{(1-\nu^2) E_m} \right\}^{1/2} = \frac{E_C}{E_m} K_{IC}^m \quad (8)$$

As more fibres are added, keeping the length $2a$ of the pre-existing crack fixed, the surface to surface separation of fibres will be of the order of the crack length (but greater than it) i.e. $S = a$ but $S > a$. For this situation (see Fig. 2) there will be significant interaction between the fibres and the local stress field associated with the crack.

Fig. 2: Small cracks embedded entirely in matrix material.

Fig. 3: Matrix crack bridged by fibres

It is no longer reasonable to regard the crack stress field as being contained entirely within matrix material. Because of the presence of fibres the crack stress field will be affected by the increase in stiffness of the material. An approximate method of accounting for this effect is to replace in (3) the matrix modulus E_m by the effective modulus E_C of the composite so that the critical applied stress to initiate cracking is

$$\sigma_c^C = \left\{ \frac{E_C g_m}{(1-\nu^2) \pi a} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

which can also be expressed, using (5), in the form

$$K_{IC} = \left\{ \frac{E_C g_m}{1 - \nu^2} \right\}^{1/2} = \left[\frac{E_C}{E_m} \right]^{1/2} K_{IC}^m \quad (10)$$

The relative sizes of the crack and the fibres are shown in Fig. 2. It is clear that as the crack first grows it passes only through matrix material and the work of fracture per unit thickness remains at the value g_m . Strictly speaking the replacement of the modulus E_m by E_C is valid only if $S \ll a$ and fibres break when they intersect the crack. However it is expected to lead to reasonable lower bounds for σ_c^C and K_{IC} for the case

$S = a$ under discussion.

Higher Volume Fractions - Continuum Model

A further increase in the fibre content of the composite, keeping the length of the pre-existing crack fixed, leads to the situation illustrated in Fig. 3 where $S < a$ and the crack is bridged by fibres which are assumed to remain intact as the material is loaded. For situations $S \ll a$ there will be a sufficient number of fibres bridging the crack for their effect to be modelled by a continuous pressure distribution which resists the opening of the crack and hence reduces the stress intensity factor associated with a given applied stress and crack length. Marshall et al [2] and McCartney [3] have considered the mechanics of cracking for this situation. The composite is assumed to behave as a linear elastic material having modulus E_C , even in the regions near the crack where fibre-matrix debonding would take place in the actual composite. The stress intensity factor is given by

$$K = 2 \sqrt{\frac{a}{\pi}} \int_0^a \frac{\sigma_\infty - p(x)}{\sqrt{(a^2 - x^2)}} dx, \quad (11)$$

where $p(x)$ is the pressure distribution modelling the effect of fibres bridging the crack. When $p(x) \equiv 0$, so that the crack surfaces are stress-free, this expression reduces to the relation (5). The value of the pressure $p(x)$ at the location x on the crack depends upon the amount of crack opening at this point.

It has been shown in some detail by McCartney [3] that for a continuum model of matrix cracking the crack driving force (per unit thickness) is $(1-\nu^2)K^2/E_C$ such that crack growth will occur only if

$$\frac{(1-\nu^2)K^2}{E_C} = g, \quad (\text{plane strain}) \quad (12)$$

where K is the stress intensity factor defined by (11) and where g is the work of fracture per unit thickness for the composite. This result is valid for any pressure distribution applied to the crack.

Crack Boundary Condition for Continuum Model

Before further progress can be made it is necessary to determine the relationship between the continuum pressure distribution $p(x)$ restraining crack opening and the opening of a crack in a continuum composite. Following the approach of Marshall et al [2] for the case of fibres, it is shown in the Appendix that for matrix cracking in a laminated (see Fig. 4) a simple micro-mechanical model leads to the following expression relating the crack opening $2U$ to the stress T carried by fibres bridging the crack

$$U = \frac{b}{2\tau} \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E_C} \frac{V_m E_m}{E_f} T^2, \quad (\text{plane strain}) \quad (13)$$

Fig.4: Matrix crack in a laminated composite

where $2b$ is the thickness of each reinforcing ply, and where τ is the frictional shear stress (assumed uniform) between the lamellae and the matrix where debonding takes place (see Fig. 5). It is noteworthy that the corresponding relation for fibres may be obtained from (13) simply by replacing b by $R/2$, where R is the fibre radius. This is because the relevant geometrical parameter is just the ratio of the area of cross-section of the reinforcing phase to the length of that part of the perimeter where debonding takes place. For a fibre of circular cross-section this ratio has the value $\pi R^2/2\pi R = R/2$ and for the laminar geometry shown in Fig. 4 it has the value $2b/2 = b$.

The result (13) is the basis of a corresponding expression relating the continuum pressure distribution $p(x)$ and the continuum crack opening distribution to be denoted by $2\Delta(x)$. Following Marshall et al [2] and McCartney [3], the mechanical equivalence between the stresses T carried by the reinforcement and the continuum pressure p is assured when

$$p(x) = V_f T(x), \quad |x| < a \quad (14)$$

where $T(x)$ is the stress carried by the reinforcement at the location x on the crack. For the case of fibre reinforcement Marshall et al [2] assume that $\Delta \equiv U$ so that their continuum crack boundary condition corresponding to (13) is, for $|x| < a$

$$\Delta(x) = \{2\pi(1-\nu^2)/E_c \bar{\lambda}^2\} p^2(x) \quad \text{where} \quad \bar{\lambda} = 2V_f \left\{ \frac{2\pi\tau}{R} \frac{E_f}{V_m E_m} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (15)$$

It is our view that it is unreasonable to assume that $\Delta \equiv U$. Because the continuum model does not have the capacity for slip at the reinforcement-matrix interfaces in the neighbourhood of the crack, we believe that the continuum crack opening must be less than the opening predicted by the micro-mechanical model i.e. $\Delta < U$.

The appropriate relationship between Δ and U will now be derived for the case of laminates. It is of fundamental importance that the effect of the material near the matrix crack where debonding has occurred (ie. between AA' and BB' in Fig. 5), on the surrounding perfectly bonded material (ie. above AA' and below BB') must be the same for both the continuum and micro-mechanical models. The relation (14) ensures that the tractions for the two models exerted on the lines AA' and BB' are identical. The additional displacement of the line AA' (or BB') resulting from the formation under constant load of the matrix crack must also be the same for the two models.

Fig.5: Diagram of matrix crack opening for a laminate

For the continuum model the material lying between AA' and the upper surface of the matrix crack is replaced by perfectly bonded material and consequently, for a crack traversing the entire cross-section, the displacement of the line AA' is equal to Δ , one half of the opening of the matrix crack. For the micro-mechanical model described in the Appendix the additional displacement of the line AA' is $D_f(l) - \epsilon l$, namely

$$\frac{1 - \nu^2 \tau}{E_f} \frac{l^2}{2b},$$

where l is the length of the debonded region (see Fig. 5). From the Appendix it follows that the opening of the matrix crack may be written

$$2U = \frac{1 - \nu^2 \tau}{E_f} \frac{E_C}{b E_m V_m} l^2,$$

and thus the additional displacement of the line AA' is $E_m V_m U / E_C$. The continuum and micro-mechanical models lead to the same value for the additional displacement of the line AA' if and only if

$$\Delta = \frac{E_m V_m}{E_c} U .$$

This relation has been established only for the case when the matrix crack formed traverses the entire cross-section. Provided that the maximum length of debonding is much less than the crack length the relation

$$\Delta(x) = \frac{V_m E_m}{E_c} U(x) , \quad |x| < a \quad (16)$$

is expected to be an excellent approximation for the case when the composite contains a crack of finite length $2a$.

On using (14) and (16), the crack boundary condition corresponding to (13) may be written for $|x| < a$

$$\Delta(x) = \{2\pi(1-\nu^2)/E_c \lambda^2\} p^2(x) \text{ where } \lambda = 2 \frac{V_f}{V_m} \left\{ \frac{\pi \tau}{b} \frac{E_f E_c}{E_m^2} \right\}^{1/2} . \quad (17)$$

A comparison of the relations (15) and (17) indicates that there is an important difference between the crack boundary condition (15) based on the approach of Marshall et al [2] and our approach. The boundary condition (17), when modified to be valid for fibre reinforcement by replacing b by $R/2$, is identical to the relation used by McCartney [3] derived by requiring that the availability of energy for matrix cracking is the same for both the micro-mechanical and continuum models. The kinematic relation (16) is thus energetically consistent whereas the assumption $\Delta = U$ of Marshall et al [2] is not. Having derived the appropriate boundary condition (17) for the continuum model of matrix cracking, numerical methods are used [3] to calculate the stress intensity factor specified by (11). The critical stress σ_∞^C , required to cause the growth of a pre-existing matrix crack of length $2a$, is calculated by making use of the relation (12). It has been shown [3] that

$$\sigma_\infty \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{3g E_c \lambda^2}{4\pi(1-\nu^2)} \right\}^{1/3} = \sigma_M , \quad \text{as } a \rightarrow \infty , \quad (18)$$

and that matrix cracking is impossible for any length of pre-existing crack if $\sigma_\infty < \sigma_M$.

Fracture Criterion for Continuum Model

For cracking in a composite where the reinforcement remains intact, the work of fracture (per unit thickness) has the value

$$g = V_m g_m ; \quad (19)$$

the factor V_m appearing because only the matrix cracks. Using (6) and (12) the fracture criterion for a continuum model of matrix cracking may be written

$$K \geq K_{IC} = \left\{ \frac{E_C V_m G_m}{1 - \nu^2} \right\}^{1/2} = \left\{ \frac{V_m E_C}{E_m} \right\}^{1/2} K_{IC}^m \quad (20)$$

In contrast Marshall et al [2] assume a fracture criterion of the form

$$K \geq K_{IC} = \frac{E_C}{E_m} K_{IC}^m \quad (21)$$

which is introduced by stating that the matrix and composite stress intensities scale as the stresses in the ratio $E_m:E_C$. A comparison shows that there is another important difference between our approach using (20) and that of Marshall et al using (21). It is worth noting that we have already encountered the expression (21) for K_{IC} for the composite when deriving (8) for a small crack embedded well within matrix material. We believe that the fracture criterion (21) is inappropriate when a matrix crack is bridged by many fibres/lamellae.

Fig. 6(a,b) illustrates the differing results predicted by the two approaches for a composite composed of 40 volume per cent of aligned carbon fibres of radius $3.5 \mu\text{m}$ and modulus $E_f = 234 \text{ GPa}$ in a matrix of modulus $E_m = 58 \text{ GPa}$ and toughness $K_{IC}^m = 2 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ which corresponds to a borosilicate glass of the type used by Prewo et al [5]. The curves for ' σ_{∞}^C ' vs ' a ' are drawn for two values of the interfacial shear stress τ , namely 10 MPa (Fig. 6a) and 60 MPa (Fig. 6b). For the lower value of τ , and an assumed pre-existing crack length ($2a$) of $40 \mu\text{m}$ (corresponding to a fracture stress of 250 MPa for unreinforced material), the cracking stress of the composite is predicted by us to be 775 MPa and by Marshall et al theory to be 930 MPa. The corresponding fracture strain of unreinforced material is 0.43%. The cracking strain of the matrix in the composite is predicted by us to be 0.6% and by Marshall et al theory to be 0.72%.

Fig.6(a): Matrix cracking stress ' σ_{∞}^C ' as a function of ' a ' when $\tau = 10 \text{ MPa}$

Fig.6(b): Matrix cracking stress ' σ_{∞}^C ' as a function of 'a' when $\tau = 60$ MPa

It is evident from Fig. 6(a,b) that the two approaches lead to the same value for the cracking stress in the limit of very long cracks. The corresponding expression for the cracking strain of the matrix in this limit is

$$\epsilon_M = \left\{ \frac{6g_m \tau V_f^2 (1-\nu^2)^2 E_f}{R V_m E_m^2 E_C} \right\}^{1/3} \quad (22)$$

which is precisely the relationship derived by Aveston et al [1] modified for conditions of plane strain.

DISCUSSION

The matrix cracking theory reviewed in this paper assumes that the fibres remain intact as the matrix crack develops. One situation where fibre failure might occur arises when the matrix crack length is large enough for the fibre stress at the centre-point of the crack to reach the critical value σ_{uf} . McCartney [3] has provided numerical results which indicate the dependence of the fibre stress on location in the crack, crack length and applied load. As the crack boundary condition (17) would suggest the fibres at the centre of the crack carry the most load. The maximum possible load in a surviving fibre at the centre of the crack is σ_{∞}/V_f (occurring when the crack is long) and consequently the condition ensuring that fibres will not break as the matrix crack traverses the specimen entirely is

$$\sigma_{\infty}^C < V_f \sigma_{uf} \quad (23)$$

where σ_{∞}^C for a given pre-existing crack of length $2a$, is obtained from numerical results such as those presented in Fig. 6(a,b). If the pre-existing defect is long enough the value of σ_{∞}^C is given by (18). Under these conditions it is found experimentally (e.g. Cooper and Sillwood [6]) that the specimen is traversed by a set of parallel cracks with a characteristic minimum spacing. If straining is continued the specimen is expected to fail when

$$\sigma_{\infty} = V_f \sigma_{uf} \cdot \quad (24)$$

The situation can arise when, for a pre-existing crack of finite length, the fibres at the centre begin to break. Further loading, or crack growth, will lead to progressive fibre failure over an increasing portion of the crack. Marshall and Evans [7] have briefly discussed this phenomenon using an approximate method of analysis.

The theory of constrained cracking, in which the effect of fibres bridging the crack is represented by a continuum pressure distribution on the crack faces, may also be applied to understanding the cracking of laminates in which one type of ply (often 90° plies) fail while the others remain intact (often 0° plies); for example, see Parvizi et al [8] and Manders et al [9]. The geometry of Fig. 7 is relevant for the consideration of this experimental work on laminates. Here the cracks are formed in the 90° ply parallel to the fibre-matrix interface and they grow in the x -direction shown in Fig. 7. The cracking of the 90° ply is detected experimentally when cracks traverse the entire width of the specimen in the x -direction. These cracks are constrained from growing by the presence of the 0° plies of thickness b . The region of debonding in the neighbourhood of the crack at the interfaces between the 0° and 90° plies is shown in Fig. 7. It should be noted that the geometry of this crack problem is similar to that which arises when a cracked plate is repaired by bonded reinforcements, as discussed by Rose [10].

Fig.7: Diagram of matrix cracking in the 90° ply of a 0° - 90° - 0° laminate

The predictions of the continuum model of matrix cracking shown in Fig. 6(a,b) are valid only if there are a sufficient number of fibres bridging the crack. For a square array of fibres of radius $3.5 \mu\text{m}$ having a 40% volume fraction it follows from (1) that the centre-to-centre separation of nearest neighbour fibres is almost $10 \mu\text{m}$. It follows from Fig. 6(a,b) that the continuum model is relevant only for long crack lengths where ACK theory [1] provides excellent predictions. Such severe restrictions are not encountered when applying the continuum theory to laminate cracking of the type illustrated in Fig. 7.

REFERENCES

1. Aveston, J., Cooper, G.A. and Kelly, A., In Conference on the Properties of Fibre Composites, National Physical Laboratory, pp. 15-26, 1971, IPC Science and Technology Press.
2. Marshall, D.B., Cox, B.N. and Evans, A.G., The mechanics of matrix cracking in brittle-matrix fibre composites, Acta Metall 1985, 33, 2013-2021.
3. McCartney, L.N., Mechanics of matrix cracking in brittle-matrix fibre-reinforced composites, Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond. 1987, A409 329-350.
4. Griffith, A.A., Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. Lond. 1920, A221, 163.
5. Prewo, K.M. Brennan, J.J. and Layden, G.K., Amer. Ceram. Soc. Bulletin, 1986, 65, 305.
6. Cooper, G.A. and Sillwood, J.M., J. Mater. Sci. 1972, 7, 325.
7. Marshall, D.B. and Evans, A.G. Proc. 5th Int. Conf. on Composite Materials (ed. W.C. Harrigan, J. Strife and A.K. Dhingra) San Diego, Calif. July 1985, p.557.
8. Parvizi, A., Garrett, K.W. and Bailey, J.E., J. Mater. Sci. 1978, 13, 195-201.
9. Manders, P.W., Chou, T-W., Jones, F.R. and Rock, J.W., J. Mater. Sci., 1983, 18, 2876.
10. Rose, L.R.F., Int. J. Fracture 1982, 18, 135.

APPENDIX

In a laminar composite (see Fig. 4) let $2b$ be the thickness of the reinforcement having modulus E_f and let $2d$ be the thickness of the matrix having modulus E_m . The matrix and reinforcement are assumed to share the same value ν of Poisson's ratio, and plane strain conditions are assumed. When a crack in matrix material forms traversing the entire cross-section of the composite the reinforcement is assumed to remain intact. Following the approach of Marshall et al [2] and McCartney [3] it can be shown that in the region of debonding (between

BB' and CC' in Fig. 5) the stress in the reinforcement is given by

$$\sigma_f(Y) = \frac{E_f \epsilon}{1 - \nu^2} + \frac{\tau}{b} Y, \quad 0 \leq Y \leq l, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where ϵ is the strain applied to the composite, τ is the interfacial shear stress and where l is the length of debonding. The corresponding stress in the matrix is

$$\sigma_m(Y) = \frac{E_m \epsilon}{1 - \nu^2} - \frac{\tau}{b} \frac{V_f}{V_m} Y, \quad 0 \leq Y \leq l. \quad (\text{A2})$$

Since $\sigma_m(l) = 0$ it follows that

$$l = \frac{b}{\tau} \frac{V_m}{V_f} \frac{E_m \epsilon}{1 - \nu^2}. \quad (\text{A3})$$

The displacement distributions for the reinforcement and matrix are given respectively by

$$D_f(Y) = \epsilon Y + \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E_f} \frac{\tau}{2b} Y^2, \quad 0 \leq Y \leq l, \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$D_m(Y) = \epsilon Y - \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E_m} \frac{V_f}{V_m} \frac{\tau}{2b} Y^2, \quad 0 \leq Y \leq l, \quad (\text{A5})$$

where the displacements are selected to be zero on the line BB' in Fig. 5. The stress T in the reinforcement at the crack centre-line CC' is $\sigma_f(l)$ which from (A1) and (A3) may be written

$$T = \frac{E_C \epsilon}{(1 - \nu^2) V_f}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

where use has been made of (2). The opening $2U$ of the matrix crack is such that

$$U = D_f(l) - D_m(l) = \frac{b}{2\tau} \frac{E_C}{1 - \nu^2} \frac{V_m}{V_f} \frac{E_m}{E_f} \epsilon^2. \quad (\text{A7})$$

The elimination of the strain ϵ using (A6) and (A7) leads to the result (13), namely

$$U = \frac{b}{2\tau} \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E_C} \frac{V_m E_m}{E_f} T^2. \quad (\text{A8})$$